

COMPARATIVE FINANCIAL EVALUATION OF TECHNICAL LOSSES IN SOUTH EASTERN NIGERIA POWER NETWORK

Obi, P.I¹, Amako, E.A², and Ezeonye, C.S³

^{1,2}Department of Electrical & Electronic Engineering, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike, Abia state, Nigeria.

³Enugu Electricity Distribution Company, Ogbaru, Anambra state, Nigeria.

patndyobi@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This paper presents the comparative analysis of technical losses on its financial assessment associated with the distribution of power in the South Eastern part of Nigeria. This analysis is performed with the aid of electrical transient and analysis program (ETAP), wherein the South Eastern Nigeria distribution network was first modeled and its load flow generated using Newton Raphson iterative load flow method for all two hundred and three (203) load buses in the network. The system technical losses are evaluated for four cases: system alone, on-load tap changes (OLTC), fixed tap and on-load tap changes (FTOLTC), and optimal capacitor placement. The results showed that when the network is operating at 100 percent (%) load demand, the system active and reactive power losses recorded were 44.33 MW and 165.3511 MVAR respectively, while they were 11.973 MW and 0.68 MVAR when capacitor banks are used in the loss reduction. The results also showed improvements of the average power factor of 74.9% lagging. The average percentage bus loading improves to 30.1% from 42.69%, while the percentage voltage drop across transmission is 5.75%. The financial assessment of these losses show the accumulative profit over a four year period in billions of naira as the system yields profit of three hundred and eighty-seven billion, four hundred and forty-three million six hundred and sixty-eight thousand naira only (₦387,443,668,000) in its first year of operation and gradually increases to one trillion, five hundred and sixty-two billion, eighty-seven million, three hundred and ninety thousand naira only (₦1,562,087,390,000) even after the installation and operation capitals are removed from the net annual loss reduction savings in naira. It is therefore recommended for the proposed rated capacitor banks to be installed at the recommended sub-stations to yield profit which could be then injected back into the generation to improve system supply in the South Eastern Nigeria electricity distribution system.

Keywords: On-Load Tap Changers (OLTC); Fixed Tap Changers and Capacitor Banks; System Losses; Financial Evaluation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Loss analysis is a critical component for efficient power supply systems. Losses in an electric power distribution system should be around 3% to 6% (Ramesh *et al.*, 2009). Generally, it has been discovered that losses in electric power distribution systems in developed countries range within 10%, while in developing countries, the range is up to 20% (Komolafe and Udofia, 2020). It is therefore advisable for stakeholders in the power sector to put more in reducing the losses on electric power distribution lines to a desired and economic level. Studies have shown that there is usually a wide margin between the total electrical energy generated from various generating plants and the total electrical energy delivered to different load centers and subsequently to the consumers at their various homes or connection points. The range of difference is as a result of power losses sustained in transporting the electric energy over the transmission and distribution networks (Dos Santos, 2006).

The term “energy losses” refers to the difference between the aggregates of energy delivered to the distribution system and the amount of energy customers are billed as per consumed. The transmission company of Nigeria (TCN) bills the Enugu Electricity Distribution Company (EEDC) thirty-eight naira only (₦38.00) for every one-kilowatt hour supplied (Global Petrol Prices, 2022). In other words, it is the aggregate of energy injected into the transmission and distribution network that are not paid for by customers, and at the end, everyone is affected by the loss of energy be it distribution company, the consumers and the nation as a whole (Antmann, 2009, Mustafa *et al.*, 2011). Losses in the power system can be attributed to losses in ageing equipment, line and transformer losses and also operation losses. Power transformers mounted at power transmission stations are used to increase the voltage from the generators, and then transformers at distribution substations decrease the voltage to supply

loads. Raising the system voltage decreases the current in the power lines and hence the conductor sizes and distribution losses. This results in distribution of power being more economical over long distances (Chinwukoet *al.*, 2011).

Technical loss is the type of loss that takes place in power transmission and distribution due to the type and nature or the physical properties of equipment used in the system, which cannot be eliminated totally. Examples of such equipment include generators and transformers. These have winding losses due to winding resistance, and core losses due to the presence of hysteresis and eddy current in the core (Omorogiuwa and Obi, 2014). Other examples of equipment that cause technical losses in power system are transmission and distribution lines. This type of loss is due to the effect of thermal current flow in the conductors, as well as corona at higher voltages (Mustafa *et al.*, 2011; Komolafe and Udofia, 2020; Obi *et al.*, 2021). Technical power losses are classified as induction and radiation losses, dielectric losses, and copper losses (I^2R). They include resistive losses of the primary and secondary feeders (11 kV, and 33 kV), resistive and core losses in windings of distribution transformers and generators, resistive losses in service drops to customers and losses in fiscal meter due to inductive load customers. These losses in power distribution are caused majorly due to improper earthing of electrical equipment such as generators and transformers, use of substandard equipment in power distribution, unbalanced loading of distribution transformer and distortion of system harmonics. It can be minimized through the use of more efficient and adequate equipment, and through optimized network design (Adesina and Ademola, 2016; Chukwulobeet *al.*, 2022).

Several researchers have carried out power loss analysis in transmission and distribution of electric energy. B-loss coefficient and Depazo methods were used to compute power system technical losses as a function of outputs of all generation (Anumaka, 2012). Economic outcome of

technical and non-technical losses in Nigeria's power transmission system which causes power outages in the country was studied in order to estimate the total losses associated with the transmission system (Amadi and Okafor, 2015). Analysis of technical and non-technical losses in Nigeria's 330 kV transmission network was carried out with the aid of Power World Simulator (PWS) (Omorogiuwa and Elechi, 2015). Assessment of energy shortages in some selected industrial cities in Nigeria due to technical losses in the distribution network and the cost implications was presented by (Amadi *et al.*, 2016; Amadi *et al.*, 2016). They recommended government legislation against vandalism and energy theft and to ascertain maximum power demand in the country when the suppressed loads are added to the grid. Assessment and evaluation of technical losses and their cost implications which cause energy shortages in distribution system of industrial and commercial cities in Nigeria were carried out by (Egwaileet *al.*, 2018). Some factors were presented from technical perspectives which are responsible for excessive electrical energy loss in Nigeria. They include inadequate metering, poor voltage control, choice of sizes of distribution conductors, prevalence of electrical faults, unbalanced loads, lack of legislation on electric energy theft. This was done in order to enable increase comprehension and drive urgent change in the nation which would help to efficiently manage energy availability and also for industrial growth (Komolafe and Udofia, 2020).

This paper therefore seeks to analyze and carry out financial evaluation on technical losses in South Eastern Nigeria power network by on-load tap changes, fixed tap and on-load tap changes and optimal capacitor placement to evaluate the different technical losses and the equivalent financial cost on the efficient supply of electricity in the South East with a view of suggesting the possible ways to mitigate the losses and improve the quality of electricity supply in the area under study.

2. METHODOLOGY

The materials used for this research work include: electrical transient and analysis program (ETAP), data from EEDC, and HP Laptop, dollar conversion rate of \$1 = ₦415 (Dollar to Naira Today, 2022).

The methods employed in the analysis are improved load shedding scenario which include classification of load types, their priorities number within the network and distances of the load centers.

2.1 Newton Raphson Iterative Load Flow Method

The Newton-Raphson method is a powerful method of solving non-linear algebraic equations and it has better and

faster convergence characteristics as stated in Equations 1 to 9 (Kothari and Nagrath, 2009).

Consider a set of n non-linear algebraic equations.

$$f_i(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = 0, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

Assuming the initial values are $x_1^0, x_2^0, \dots, x_n^0$. Let $\Delta x_1^0, \Delta x_2^0, \dots, \Delta x_n^0$ be the corrections to be added to the initial values to give the actual solution Equation (1) becomes.

$$f_i(x_1^0 + \Delta x_1^0, x_2^0 + \Delta x_2^0, \dots, x_n^0 + \Delta x_n^0) = 0, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Hence, } f^0 + J^0 \Delta x^0 = 0 \quad \dots \quad (3) \quad \Delta P = J_1 * \Delta \delta \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

$$\text{and, } f^0 = -J^0 \Delta x^0 \quad \dots \quad (4) \quad \Delta Q = J_4 * \Delta |V| \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta P \\ \Delta Q \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} J_1 & J_2 \\ J_3 & J_4 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta \delta \\ \Delta |V| \end{bmatrix} \quad \dots \quad (5) \quad \text{Further solving the new estimated for bus voltage magnitude and angles are,}$$

$$|V_i|^{(r+1)} = |V_i|^{(r)} + \Delta |V_i|^{(r)} \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

$$\delta_i^{(r+1)} = \delta_i^{(r)} + \Delta \delta_i^{(r)} \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

Since the R/X ratio of the line is very low J_2, J_3 is negligible.

The real power mismatch, ΔP is very sensitive to changes in the phase angle $\Delta \delta$ and less sensitive to changes in the voltage magnitude, $\Delta |V|$. The reactive power mismatch, ΔQ is very sensitive to changes in the voltage magnitude, $\Delta |V|$ and less sensitive to changes in the phase angle $\Delta \delta$. Hence Equation (5) becomes,

Where

$J_1, J_2, J_3,$ and J_4 are the elements of Jacobian matrix

2.2 Network for the analysis

The bus structure of the South East distribution network and its sub networks are shown in Figure 1.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Results of Busbar Loading and Network Losses for the Network Operating on Full-Load

When the South Eastern network is operating on full load there are two hundred and three (203) loads connected in the system. The results of its load flow analysis for the percentage busbar loading data is shown in Figures 2 to 4, and the total load demand of the South Eastern distribution network is 647.012 MVA (i.e. 517.921 MW and 387.792 MVAR) at an average power factor of 80.1%. The average percentage bus loading is 42.69%, incurring a total system loss of 44.33 MW and 165.35 MVAR in the South Eastern Nigeria power network. The financial

implication of these technical losses amounts to fourteen billion, seven hundred and sixteen million, one hundred and forty-one thousand, four hundred and forty naira only (₦ 14,716,141,440) over a year. In Figure 2, the 11 kV percentage busbar loading profile shows that only fourteen (14) buses out of one hundred and fifty-four (154) load buses are operating at above 100% requirement i.e. they are overloaded. While in Figure 3, only the Egbu 33kV bus is overloaded in the 33kV percentage bus loading. In Figure 4, the 6.6 kV bus (Ehi road Aba) is operating at stable loading in the 100% operating load case.

Figure 2: 11 kV percentage bus loading for full load case.

Figure 3: 33 kV percentage bus loading for full load case

Figure 4: 6.6 kV percentage bus loading for full load case

3.2 Results of Transformer Tap Changes on Financial Evaluation for Network Losses

When on-load tap changes is applied to the high voltage transmission end (6 transformer units of ratings 330/132 kV) of the SouthEastern network when operating on full load, as shown in the AppendixA; Table A1, total system loss increased to 47.3 MW and 101.81 MVAR and was recorded. The financial implication of these technical losses amounts to fifteen billion, seven hundred and two million, eighty-six thousand, four hundred naira only (₦15,702,086,400) over a year, with an average percentage power factor, percentage loading of the transformer and percentage voltage drop across the transformer of 74.94%, 55.47% and 4.17% respectively were recorded as seen in

Table 1. A further adjustment of both fixed tap and on-load tap changes is applied at the high voltage transmission end of the SouthEastern Nigeria network. The fixed tap is set at 2.5% for the six (6) transformer units of ratings 330/132 kV as shown in AppendixA; Table A1. The results show that a reduced total system loss of 40.1 MW and 81.24 MVAR was recorded. The financial implication of these technical losses reduces to thirteen billion, three hundred and eleven million, nine hundred and sixteen thousand, eight hundred naira only (₦13,311,916,800) over a year, while percentage power factor, percentage loading of the network and percentage voltage drop across the network improves to 75.3%, 56.4% and 3.98% respectively as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Results of tap changes on technical and financial losses of the South East network

	Total Network Loss	% PF	% loading	% Voltage Drop across the network	Financial Losses
On-Load Tap Changes (OLTC)	47.3 MW, 101.81 MVAR	▲ 74.94	▲ 55.47	▲ 4.17	₦ 15,702,086,400 ▲
Fixed Tap and On-Load Tap Changes (OLTC)	40.1 MW, 81.24 MVAR	▲ 75.30	▲ 56.40	▲ 3.98	₦ 13,311,916,800 ▼

3.3 Results of Optimal Capacitor Placement on Financial Evaluation for Network Losses

A total of seventy nine (79) 132 kV, 50Hz, 25 MVAR outdoor capacitor banks with maximum bank sizes of 10 banks were placed at the following 132 kV candidate buses: Aba control, Abakaliki TCN, Agu-Awka TCN, Egbu transmission, New Haven TCN, Nibo(Awka) TCN, Nkalagu TCN, Nsukka, Ohiya TCN and Onitsha TCN as shown in Appendix A; Figure A1 and Table A2. These total of seventy-nine(79) capacitor banks applied had a capacity released of 149.017 MVA into the South East grid with Onitsha TCN – Nibo/Awka 132 kV transmission line the biggest beneficiary with a release of 15.989 MVA into its grid as shown in Appendix A; Table A3. The total

power losses of the South Eastern distribution network reduced severely to 11.973 MW and 0.68 MVAR, with an average power factor of 74.9% lagging. The average percentage bus loading improves to 30.1% and percentage voltage drop across transmission is 5.75% as shown in Table 2. The financial implication of these technical losses amounted to three billion, nine hundred and seventy four million, six hundred and fifty two thousand, eight hundred and sixty four naira only (₦3,974,652,864) annually, a drastic reduction from the previous two cases (system with tap changes and system operating at full load without transformer alterations).

Table 2: Results of optimal capacitor placement on technical and financial losses of the South East Network

Total Network Loss	% PF	% loading	% Voltage Drop across the network	Financial Losses
--------------------	------	-----------	-----------------------------------	------------------

Optimal Capacitor Placement	11.973 MW, 0.68 MVAR	▲ 74.9	▼ 30.1	▼ 5.75	₦ 3,974,652,864 ▼
------------------------------------	----------------------	--------	--------	--------	-------------------

3.4 Comparison of Results for the Different Case Scenarios on Financial Evaluation for Network Losses

The Table 3 shows the comparative results of the different case scenarios on technical and financial losses of the South Eastern Nigeriannetwork. It shows a reduction in the total network active and reactive power losses from 44.33 MW and 165.35 MVAR when the system is operating on full load (default) to 40.1 MW and 81.24 MVAR respectively when the system is on fixed tap and on-load tap changes and finally the active and reactive power losses reduced severely to 11.973 MW and 0.68 MVAR when optimal capacitor banks are placed in the system. Table 3 also shows an improvement in both average percentage power factor of 74.9% lagging and the average

percentage bus loading improves to 30.1% from 42.69% at default. The average percentage voltage drop across transmission reduced from 6.49% to 4.147%and finally to 5.73%on application of optimal capacitor banks as presented in Table 3. The financial implication of these technical losses severely reduced to three billion, nine hundred and seventy-four million, six hundred and fifty-two thousand, eight hundred and sixty-four naira only (₦3,974,652,864) annuallyfrom fourteen billion, seven hundred and sixteen million, one hundred and forty-one thousand, four hundred and forty naira only (₦ 14,716,141,440) when the system is operating alone without any transformer alterations.

Table 3: Comparative results of case scenarios on technical and financial losses of the South East Network

Case scenarios	Total Network Loss (Active and Reactive)	% PF	% loading	% Voltage Drop across the network	Financial Losses
System Alone (default)	44.33 MW and 165.35 MVAR	80.1	42.69	6.49	₦ 14,716,141,440
On-Load Tap Changes (OLTC)	▲ 47.3 MW, 101.81 MVAR	▲ 74.94	▲ 55.47	▲ 4.17	₦ 15,702,086,400 ▲
Fixed Tap and On-Load Tap Changes (OLTC)	▼ 40.1 MW, 81.24 MVAR	▲ 75.30	▲ 56.40	▲ 3.98	₦ 13,311,916,800 ▼
Optimal Capacitor Placement	▼ 11.973 MW, 0.68 MVAR	▲ 74.9	▼ 30.1	▼ 5.75	₦ 3,974,652,864 ▼

3.5 Results of Optimal Capacitor Placement Cost to Network Loss Savings Analysis

The optimal capacitor placement cost to savings analysis was performed for the seventy-nine (79) 132 kV, 50Hz, 25 MVAR outdoor capacitor banks inserted into the network over a four (4) year planning period as shown in Table 4. An installation cost of one thousand five hundreddollar only (\$1,500) per station, purchase price of one million, two hundred and fifty thousand dollar only(\$1,250,000) and five hundred dollar(\$500) operational cost per year per capacitor bank per station. The total cost of installation (cost of purchase and cost of operation of the installed capacitor banks) amounted to four billion, one hundred and four million three hundred and fiftythousand naira only (₦4,104,350,000)and sixteen billion, three hundred and ninety-two million five hundred thousand naira only (₦16,392,500,000) respectively. After a period of four (4) years, the accumulated profit saved by the transmission

company amounts to one trillion, five hundred and sixty two billion, eighty-seven million three hundred and ninety thousand naira only (₦1,562,087,390,000) while yearly loss reduction is three hundred and ninety one billion, five hundred and forty-eight millioneighteen thousand naira only (₦391,548,018,000)with the use of the capacitor banks as shown in Table 4. Figure 5 shows the comparison of the annual loss reduction between the use of capacitor banks, use of transformer tap changes and when the network is operating without any alterations. It shows the amount of money lost by the system technical losses for the four case studies indicating that the use of optimal capacitor banks placement produced the smallest technical losses. Figure 6 shows the accumulative profit over a four-year period in billions of naira as the system yields profit in its first year of operation even after the installation and operation capitals are removed from the net annual loss reduction savings in naira.

Table 4: Optimal Capacitor Placement Cost to Savings

Year	Cost (₦)		Annual Saving (₦)		
	Installation	Operation	Loss Reduction	Yearly Profit	Accumulative Profit
1	4,104,350,000.00 ▼	16,392,500.00	391,564,369,000.00	387,443,668,000.00	387,443,668,000.00 ▲
2	-	16,392,500.00	391,564,369,000.00	391,548,018,000.00	778,991,520,000.00 ▲

3	-	16,392,500.00	391,564,369,000.00	391,548,018,000.00	1,170,539,455,000.00 ▲
4	-	16,392,500.00	391,564,369,000.00	391,548,018,000.00	1,562,087,390,000.00 ▲

Figure 5: Financial cost of network losses (in billions of naira)

Figure 6: Accumulative profit over a four year period (in billions of naira)

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper the technical losses have been evaluated alongside its financial implications for the South Eastern Nigeria electricity supply. The use of different loss/MVAR reduction methods such as on-load tap changes, fixed tap and on-load tap changes and optimal capacitor placement to evaluate their different technical losses and the equivalent financial cost on the efficient supply of electricity in the South Eastern Nigeria. The results discussed herein showed that system total active and reactive power losses reduced from 44.33 MW and 165.35 MVAR to 47.3 MW and 101.81 MVAR respectively when the transformers are operating on-load tap changes and finally to 11.973 MW and 0.68 MVAR when capacitor banks are used in the loss reduction. The results showed improvements of the average power factor of 74.9% lagging. The average percentage bus loading improved to 30.1% and percentage voltage drop across transmission is 5.75%. The

financial assessment of these losses and improvement across the four cases show the accumulative profit over a four year period in billions of naira as the system yields profit of three hundred and eight-seven billion, four hundred and forty-three million six hundred and sixty-eight thousand naira only (N387,443,668,000) in its first year of operation even after the installation and operation capitals are removed from the net annual loss reduction savings in naira. In a nutshell, it has been seen that the use of optimal capacitor placement reduces the network losses by the greatest value and still yields profit as its loss reduction upturns its initial capital. It is therefore recommended for the proposed rated capacitor banks to be installed at the recommended sub-stations to yield profit which could be then injected back into the generation to improve system supply in the South Eastern Nigeria electricity distribution system.

REFERENCES

Adesina, L. M. and Ademola, A. (2016). Determination of Power System Losses in Nigerian Electricity Distribution Networks. *International Journal of Engineering and Technology*, Vol. 6, No. 9, pp. 322-326.

Amadi, H. N. and Okafor, E. N.C. (2015). The Effects of Technical and Non-Technical Losses on Power Outages in Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, Vol. 6, No. 9, pp. 45-49.

Amadi, H. N., Izuegbunam, F. I. and Okafor, E. N. C. (2016). Evaluation of Losses in Distribution Networks of Selected Industrial Cities in Nigeria Using ETAP. *British Journal of Applied Science & Technology*, Vol. 17, No. 6, pp. 1-12.

Amadi, H. N., Okafor, E. N. C. and Izuegbunam, F. I. (2016). Assessment of Energy Losses and Cost Implications in the Nigerian Distribution Network.

- American Journal of Electrical and Electronic Engineering*, Vol. 4, No. 5, pp. 123-130.
- Antmann, P. (2009). Reducing Technical and Non-Technical losses in Power Sector. Background Paper for the world Bank Group Energy Sector Stratage, World Bank, Washington, DC. <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/> accessed on 25th October, 2021.
- Anumaka, M. C. (2012). Analysis of Technical Losses in Electrical Power System (Nigerian 330 kV Network as a Case Study). *International Journal of Research and Review in Applied Sciences (IJRRAS)*, Vol. 12, No. 2, pp. 320-327.
- Chinwuko, E. C., Nwuba, U. and Mgbemena, C. O. (2011). Optimum Reliability and Cost of Power Distribution System: A Case of Power Holding Company of Nigeria. *International Journal of Engineering Science & Technology*. Vol. 3, No. 11, pp. 7934-7941.
- Chukwulobe, O. O., Obi, P. I., Amako, E. A. and Ezeonye, C. S. (2022). Improved Under-Voltage Load Shedding Scheme in Power System Network for South Eastern Nigeria. *NIPES Journal of Science and Technology Research*, Vol. 4, No. 1, pp. 212-223.
- Dollar to Naira Today. (2022). US Dollar to Naira Chart <https://www.ngnrates.com/exchange-rates/us-dollar-to-naira> accessed on 24th January, 2022.
- Dos Santos, C. M. P. (2006). Determination of Electric Power Losses in Distribution Systems. *IEEE/PES Transmission & Distribution Conference and Exposition: Latin America*, 15-18 August, 2006, Caracas, Venezuela, pp. 1-5.
- Egwaile, J., Ogbeide, K. and Osahenvemwen, A. (2018). Technical Loss Estimation and Reduction in a Typical Nigerian Distribution System: A Case Study. *Journal of Electrical Engineering, Electronics, Control and Computer Science – JEECCS*, Vol. 4, No. 13, pp. 1-8.
- Global Petrol Prices. (2022). Nigeria Electricity Prices. https://www.globalpetrolprices.com/Nigeria/electricity_prices/ accessed on 24th January, 2022.
- Komolafe, O. M. and Udofia, K. M. (2020). Review of Electrical Energy Losses in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Technology (NIJOTECH)*, Vol. 39, No. 1, pp. 246-254.
- Kothari, D. P. and Nagrath, I. J. (2009). *Modern Power System Analysis*, 3rd Edition, McGraw-Hill Inc., New Delhi, India.
- Mustafa, S. S., Yasen, M. H. and Abdullah, H. H. (2011). Evaluation of Electric Energy Losses in Kirkuk Distribution Electric System Area. *Iraq Journal of Electrical and Electronic Engineering*, Vol. 7, No. 2, pp. 144-150.
- Obi, P. I., Amako, E. A. and Ezeonye, C. S. (2021). Investigating the Characteristics of Corona Effect on AC Transmission Line with Variation of Line Parameters. *Bayero Journal of Engineering and Technology (BJET)*, Vol. 16, No. 3, pp. 1-8.
- Omorogiuwa, E. and Elechi, P. (2015). Economic Effects of Technical and Non-Technical Losses in Nigeria Power Transmission System. *IOSR Journal of Electrical and Electronics Engineering (IOSR-JEEE)*, Vol. 10, No. 2, pp. 89-100.
- Omorogiuwa E. and Obi, P. I. (2014). Modelling of Underground Cables for High Voltage Transmission. *International Journal of Engineering and Science (IJES)*, Vol. 5, Issue 12, pp. 57-67.
- Ramesh, L., Chowdhury, S. P., Chowdhury, S., Natarajan, A. A. and Gaunt, C. T. (2009). Minimization of Power loss in Distribution Networks by different Techniques. *International Journal of Power and Energy Systems Engineering*, Vol. 2, No. 1, pp. 1-6.
- Turkay, B. (1998). Distribution System Planning using Mixed Integer Programming. *Elektrik*, Vol. 6, No. 1, pp. 37-48.

APPENDIX A

Table A1: Fix tap and on-load tap changes transformer settings

	Case I		Case II	
	% Load Tap Change (OLTC)	% Fixed Tap	% Load Tap Change (OLTC)	% Fixed Tap
Enugu T1	10	-	8.125	2.5
Enugu T2	8.125	-	6.25	2.5
Alaoji T1	10	-	10	2.5
Alaoji T2	10	-	10	2.5
Onitsha T1	10	-	10	2.5
Onitsha T2	10	-	10	2.5

Figure A1: Candidate buses for optimal capacitor placement showing capacitor bank ratings

Table A2: Optimal capacitor placement results

Optimal Capacitor Placement Results											
Candidate Buses					Capacitor Information						
ID	Operating Voltage				Rated kvar/Bank	Rated kV	# of Banks	Total kvar	Cost (\$)		
	Nominal kV	% Mag.	Angle	% PF					Installation	Purchase	Oper./Year
Aba Control	132.000	89.099	-5.91	66.1	2500.000	132.000	10	25000.000	1500.00	1250000.00	5000.00
Abakaliki TCN	132.000	81.292	-11.36	94.9	2500.000	132.000	10	25000.000	1500.00	1250000.00	5000.00
AguAwka TCN	132.000	79.253	-14.09	94.0	2500.000	132.000	10	25000.000	1500.00	1250000.00	5000.00
Egbu Transmission	132.000	85.775	-7.87	76.6	2500.000	132.000	8	20000.000	1500.00	1000000.00	4000.00
New Heaven TCN	132.000	89.402	-7.44	79.6	2500.000	132.000	10	25000.000	1500.00	1250000.00	5000.00
Nibo(Awka) TCN	132.000	79.854	-13.46	85.5	2500.000	132.000	9	22500.000	1500.00	1125000.00	4500.00
Nkalagu TCN	132.000	86.804	-9.49	81.4	2500.000	132.000	2	5000.000	1500.00	250000.00	1000.00
Nsukka	132.000	78.486	-14.86	99.3	2500.000	132.000	6	15000.000	1500.00	750000.00	3000.00
Ohiya TS	132.000	89.196	-6.42	84.4	2500.000	132.000	8	20000.000	1500.00	1000000.00	4000.00
Onitsha Trans Station	132.000	82.356	-11.33	73.3	2500.000	132.000	6	15000.000	1500.00	750000.00	3000.00
						Total	79	197500.000	15000.00	9875000.00	39500.00

Table A3: Branch capacity release report

Branch		Capacity Release (MVA)		
ID	Type	Maximum Loading	Minimum Loading	Average Loading
Line24	Line	11.109	13.561	12.495
Line58	Line	5.992	3.792	5.412
Line51	Line	2.912	3.743	3.558
Line72	Line	8.302	7.448	8.699
Line53	Line	0.000	0.000	0.000
ALAOJI T1	2W XFMR	11.974	13.932	13.192
ALAOJI T2	2W XFMR	14.369	16.718	15.830
Line54	Line	7.155	8.029	7.782
Line55	Line	5.312	7.658	6.620
Line60	Line	18.465	11.003	15.724
ENUGU T1	2W XFMR	7.284	9.223	8.440
ENUGU T2	2W XFMR	7.284	9.223	8.440
Line59	Line	6.815	7.855	7.646
Line52	Line	14.738	15.386	15.989
Line48	Line	2.808	-0.835	1.467
ONITSHA T1	2W XFMR	6.442	10.786	8.861
ONITSHA T2	2W XFMR	6.442	10.786	8.861
Total		137.404	148.307	149.017